

November newsletter

It's November already. This month we share UKRN resources and shine a spotlight on Aston University. There are open calls for talks at 2 events early next year, journal club paper recommendations, events for your diary and a gift suggestion for the Christmas shoppers amongst you.

Hot off the press! An exciting opportunity to work on the STAPLE project. Funded by NASA, it really is rocket science.

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Please read on...and let us know what you think.

Get involved with STAPLE

[Science Tracking Across the Project Lifespan](#) (STAPLE) is a new research project creating a project management tool for large scale research projects that not only helps with the unique challenges of project management of research but includes open and transparent documentation of data and metadata. Learn more [here](#).

STAPLE is under development by Erin Buchanan, Marton Kovacs, and others.

If you would like to become a tester please contact [staple.helpdesk\[at\]gmail.com](mailto:staple.helpdesk[at]gmail.com)

UKRN Resource - Open Research across Disciplines

The UKRN website hosts a wealth of resources including a section on [Open Research across Disciplines](#)

This can help people new to open research learn how to apply open research practices to their research, and help everyone learn more about open research practices within other disciplines.

This [substantial document](#) (58 pages!) lists case studies of open research per discipline, and resources per discipline (including open methods, open data, open output and open education). Each page includes a link to suggest changes or additions.

These pages are adapted and extended from: Farran, E. K., Silverstein, P., Ameen, A. A., Misheva, I., & Gilmore, C. (2020, December 15) Open Research: Examples of good practice, and resources across disciplines.

Spotlight on Aston University...

... with Lecturer Dr Charlotte Pennington

Our [recent blog](#) spotlights open research activities at Aston University and the work of LNL Charlotte Pennington. Learn about the Local Network at Aston, the range of LNL activities, Charlotte's new book [A Student's Guide to Open Science](#) and her hopes for the LNL Community Project.

Undergraduate student final year dissertation consortia

Charlotte has spearheaded a 'consortium approach' to the undergraduate dissertation project. A consortium brings final year students and supervisors from several institutions together to work on a shared project. A Cardiff, Bath, Bristol, and Exeter consortium has been running since 2017, with Charlotte being involved since 2019 at UWE Bristol and now Aston University. The consortium typically has around 5 supervisors from different universities, each with between 2 -6 students. The consortium pools resources to overcome the limits typically associated with undergraduate final year dissertations, for example increasing the typical sample size that can be collected by individual students and overcoming the limitations of time and funding. This means more heads working on a problem, expertise and skills being shared, and makes research more efficient. A consortium can lead to a robust, large-scale publishable project. This can help graduates' prospects because they have a pre-registered report and publication, as well as a myriad of skills that encompass 'big team science' for example visualisation and data analysis.

Consortia can also be run internally to test the model, for example a mini-consortium with 2 supervisors within a department, before going on to work with external partners.

Merging pre-print and final paper DOIs to allow combined citations

Here's a top tip from Charlotte's book: Archived preprints gather citations, but when the paper is published in its final form the journal citation count starts at zero. Charlotte highlights a way to merge preprint and final paper DOIs, for example within Google Scholar, to enable these citations to be combined and tracked. This has the added benefit of tying the preprint to the final published article, so the reader can transparently see any changes between them.

Read more about undergraduate consortia and merging DOIs [here](#).

Journal club paper recommendations

In need of inspiration? Here are some paper recommendations for you. Thanks to Lianne Wolsink, a PhD student in the Department of Cognitive Psychology, Ruhr University Bochum, Germany for these. You can find Lianne on X (Formerly known as Twitter) @LianneWolsink

Organised by: Gen Hartanto, George Jacob, Robert Reichert, and Lianne Wolsink

Theme	Article
Big Little Lies: Recap and Introduction	Stefan A. M. & Schönbrodt F. D. (2023). Big Little Lies: A Compendium and Simulation of p-hacking Strategies. <i>Royal Society Open Science</i> , 10, 220346.
Reveal, Don't Conceal: Data Visualization	Weissgerber T. L. et al. (2019). Reveal, Don't Conceal: Transforming Data Visualization to Improve Transparency. <i>Circulation</i> , 40,1506–1518.
Bias Be Gone: Pre-registrations	Hardwicke T. E. & Wagenmakers E. J. (2023). Reducing bias, increasing transparency and calibrating confidence with preregistration. <i>Nature Human Behaviour</i> , 7, 15–26.
Across the Multiverse	Steen S., Tuerlinckx F., Gelman A., & Vanpaemel W. (2016). Increasing Transparency Through a Multiverse Analysis. <i>Perspectives on Psychological Science</i> , 11, 702–712.
I'm All About That Bayes	Etz A. & Vandekerckhove J. (2016). A Bayesian Perspective on the Reproducibility Project: Psychology. <i>PLOS ONE</i> , 11, e0149794.
Beyond Hypotheses: Highlighting Nonconfirmatory Research	Scheel A. M., Tiokhin L., Isager P. M., & Lakens D. (2021). Why Hypothesis Testers Should Spend Less Time Testing Hypotheses. <i>Perspectives on Psychological Science</i> , 16, 744–755.

First Registered Report in Nature Methods

In October 2023 Nature Methods published their first [Registered Report](#), a quantitative comparative analysis of near-infrared fluorescent proteins (FPs). The journal published a commentary on the process - [Registered Reports: What](#)

[we've learned so far](#). The authors have also provided their [perspective](#), their goal being the establishment of standardized protocols and benchmarks for the swiftly moving field of FPs to help users select the appropriate FP for a variety of research applications thus saving time, resources and streamlining experimental design.

Image credit: 12019 - Pixabay

Events

Here's a quick round up of upcoming events, several of which are linked to Open Research Week 2023. Check out the [Open Research Calendar](#) for more events, and don't forget to add your own here too.

UKRN webinar

[Accelerating Open Research Practices – How the Open Research Programme is creating change](#)

Thursday 16 November 1:00 pm - 3:00 pm

The last update on the UKRN Open Research Programme was in February, and much has happened since as it accelerates open research by providing

training, reforming policies, enabling sharing of practice and developing insights and indicators. This webinar will present a summary of recent developments in the Programme, highlight some discussion points to inform its next phase, and give attendees a chance to ask questions.

Speakers:

Neil Jacobs, Head of UKRN's Open Research Programme

Anna Korzeniowska, OR4 Project on reforming staff recruitment and promotion to reward and recognise open research

Conference

[Open Research for Inclusion: Spotlighting Different Voices in Open Research at Cambridge](#)

Friday 17 November 2023

This hybrid one-day conference will focus on areas of Open Research in under-represented disciplines and contexts which have been at the forefront of recent discussions in Cambridge. These include Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences, the GLAM sector (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums), and research from and about the Global South. More information including programme details, registration and speaker abstracts is available [here](#)

Webinar

[How to Share Research Data: Examples from Engineering and Human Sciences](#)

Tuesday 21 November 11:00am – 12:30pm

This webinar from Aalto University is aimed at university staff and students who would like to explore new ways for initiating research cooperation. This is a step-by-step demonstration on how to publish a dataset in Zenodo, and how to publish metadata in the Aalto Current Research Information System. After attending this webinar, you will be more aware of dedicated platforms for sharing research data and research data metadata, such as [zenodo.org](#) and [research.aalto.fi](#), and you will master the basics of uploading and properly describing your own data.

Instructors:

Clemens Icheln, University Lecturer, Docent, D.Sc. (Tech.), Data Agent

Laura Mure, Information Specialist, Aalto Research Services

Q&A Webinar

[Study Pre-Registration and Registered Reports \(Q&A\)](#)

Thursday 23 November 11:00am - 12:00pm

Aalto University have produced a [training video](#) about Study Pre-Registration and Registered Reports. This webinar Q&A session is a chance to ask questions about the video and the topic more broadly.

Instructor: **Enrico Glerean**, Data Agent & Staff Scientist, School of Science, Aalto University.

Image credit: Steve Cliff - Pixabay

Webinar

[How to build an open research community: Inter-institutional perspectives](#)

Wednesday 29 November 2023 12:00 - 1:00pm

An Open Research Conversation from the University of Sheffield. How do we best support the development of grass-roots open research communities? In this session, researchers and research-related colleagues from a range of institutions share their experiences of the key considerations and strategies that inform open research community-building.

Speakers:

Neil Shephard - University of Sheffield

Lufti Bin Othman and **Kim Clugston** - University of Cambridge

Hardy Schwamm - University of Galway

Save the date: 4 - 15 March 2024

Scientific meeting - [What in the world is going on with open access and open research?](#)

The online Oxford Forum of Open Scholarship (OxFOS) covers a range of topical issues for a fortnight each year. The third OxFOS will run between the 4-15 March 2024. The planning committee invites responses to a [call for papers](#), open until **13th November 2023**. Submissions must discuss current Open Scholarship: Open Research, Open Access, or Research Data.

Save the date: 4 & 5 March 2024

Scientific meeting - [The promises and pitfalls of preregistration](#)

This London (and online) meeting will bring together speakers from a range of disciplines, including psychology, social sciences, philosophy, history of science, statistics, and medicine. The aim of the meeting is to explore the epistemological and pragmatic dimensions of preregistration, identify potential limits of application, and develop a practical agenda to guide future research and optimise implementation.

You are invited to submit posters or lightning talks on the topic of preregistration to our open call - **deadline 30th November**. Instructions are available on the [meeting website](#).

Christmas gift recommendation

Data isn't just for Christmas but it could be a good place to start. Here is a recommendation from Joseph Mackereth published in Nightingale, the Journal of the Data Visualization Society, earlier this year: a book by Gulrez Khan called [‘Drawing Data with Kids, cultivating data-literacy: a screen-free journey through the art of visualization for kids’](#).

Get involved

We'd love to hear from you. Let us share what you've been doing. Would you like to be a guest editor? Get in touch contact@ukrn.org

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